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EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE MEASUREMENT SELECTING

ABSTRACT

In recent decades, the interest of theorists and researchers in emotional intelligence has increased at times compared to that in IQ. Theoretical work has hypothesized that emotional intelligence is more than just cognitive intelligence and is likely measured by methods other than those that consider only IQ. Different authors impose and defend different concepts related to the understanding and study of emotional intelligence. This article presents the time-established, theoretically-based instruments for measuring emotional intelligence level as well as other popular instruments. The theoretical review of the models is not touched upon, but the emphasis is on the questionnaires measuring emotional intelligence and the comparison between them.

KEY WORDS

Emotional intelligence, EI measurement tools, MSCEIT, ESCI, EQ-I, TEIQue

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INTRODUCTION

In the years since 1990, the core concepts of emotional intelligence (EI) have been defined and continue to be relevant and underpin the research that is conducted. This time span

covers the last three periods distinguished by Mayer. This is when the most popular and scientifically sound models and understandings of EI emerged.

Understanding EI does not lead to a single established way of looking at this concept. Different scholars and researchers advocate different theories about the meaning, components, and measurement of EI, and they integrate their findings into models and to each of these.

KEY MEASURES OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Measuring EI as an ability

This model defines EI as a set of abilities that can be measured using a test composed of questions with correct and incorrect answers.

Measuring emotional intelligence with MSCEIT

John Mayer, Peter Salovey, and David Caruso (2003) first developed a methodology to study emotional intelligence in 2001 (MSCEIT, v1.0). Over time, they refined and improved this methodology, and in 2002 the MSCEIT, v2.0 (The Mayer Salovey Caruso Emotional Intelligence

Test) appeared. There are 141 questions in this test, and they are grouped into 8 sections, two for each of the described ramifications of the model. This methodology is proving to be balanced, consistent and shows good psychometric results, which is why it is gaining wide popularity. The test is still in use today and is promoted as a tool necessary in the selection of quality personnel.

Description of MSCEIT

The constructed test responds to their popular theoretical model and its questions are in four branches. The first examines the perception and expression of emotions, and respondents are asked to identify the emotions on the faces of people shown in a photograph. The second ramification, use of emotions in the thought process, is measured with questions that assess people's ability to describe their emotional sensations with their parallels and other sensory modalities. The third component of the model measures a person's ability to analyse mixed or complex emotions, to understand how emotional responses change over time, and to be able to track the sequence of different emotions. The final component of the model assesses how participants manage the emotions of others and how they regulate their own emotions.

MSCEIT implementation features

MSCEIT scoring is objective in nature, as there are better and worse answers. There are also two types of scoring on this test, which are consensus or expert. Consensus scoring compares the scores achieved with those of a normative set that reflects the responses of over 5000 people from different parts of the world. These responses are collected from a large, heterogeneous sample of individuals. In the other variant, expert norms were obtained from a sample of twenty-one members of the International Society for Research on Emotions (ISRE), who provided their expert judgment on each of the test items.

Mixture models for EI measurement

This is a concept of emotional intelligence proposed by Daniel Goleman, and by Reuven Bar-On. They consider as components not only cognitive abilities and emotional states, but also motivation, nonverbal dispositions, personality traits, and personal and social skills. The combination of personality traits, abilities, and behavioral patterns of social adjustment, according to many authors, can be defined as an appropriate basis for constructing "mixed" models of emotional intelligence.

Daniel Goleman's ECI model

EI measurement tools based on Goleman's theoretical model have undergone significant changes since their inception and have improved over time. The *Emotional Competence Inventory* (ECI) is built on competencies that allow a person to demonstrate intelligent use of their emotions in managing themselves and working with others to be effective at work (Boyatzis, Goleman and Rhee, 2000). At the time of its creation, existing assessment methods, such as simulations and interviews, in assessment centers no longer provided accurate information. The methodology was designed for ease of use and so that a specific measurement tool could be used for elements of the theoretical model. This also enables individual results achieved in completing the questionnaire to be objectively compared with the results of others.

Description of ECI

In designing their questionnaire, the authors Richard Boyatzis and Daniel Goleman used an existing competency assessment questionnaire created by Boyatzis in 1991 called the Self-Assessment Questionnaire (Boyatzis, 1994). The authors redesigned some of the questions to address the non-cognitive abilities included in the model and so make up about 40% of the new methodology and the remaining 60% are from entirely new questions (Spenser and Spenser, 1993). The subsequent validation of the methodology involved 596 respondents from different fields of work - managers,

sales engineers etc. Based on the reliability analysis and correlations from the results obtained, the components were revised.

In 1999, a version of the ECI was published, with the participation of researchers from the Hay/Mcber Group, who contributed their experience gained after numerous studies in the field.

The theoretical understanding of EI, the subsequent initial empirical model and the current measurement model also have some differences between them. In the theoretical model, the components under study are divided into five groups, in the initial model three, in the subsequent model and in the current empirical model four.

Despite the efforts of the authors, the ECI methodology has some major drawbacks that can be avoided. These include:

- The methodology can be assessed as reliable, but in the data presented after the validation, there are very high correlations between some of the competency groups. This leads to a loss of differentiation and threatens to perceive the concept of EI as a collection of disparate components rather than a unified assessment system.
- The validity of the test is also uncertain in the presence of the above.
- The test contains too many questions (110), which requires a lot of time to complete the whole questionnaire and leads to reluctance.

These may be some of the reasons that led to the revision of the methodology and the creation of ECI 2.0. The new instrument measures 18 competencies divided into four groups as follows:

- Self-awareness - knowledge of inner states, preferences, resources and intuitions.
- Self-management - management of internal states, resources and impulses.
- Social engagement - focuses on how people relate to each other and how aware they are of the feelings, needs and concerns of others.
- Relationship management - the skill of eliciting desired responses from others

The Likert scale used for the input of the answers has also changed from the seven- grade scale used in the first version of the methodology to a six-grade scale. The number of questions in the two versions of the model also differ. The ECI v1.0 has 110 items rated on a seven-point Likert scale and the ECI v2.0 has 72 items. The ECI v1.0 consists of 20 dimensions (referred to as competencies) organized into 4 clusters, while the v2.0 consists of 18 competencies.

The development of the instrument undergoes further changes. The reason for this is the authors' distinction of social from emotional intelligence. The Emotional and Social Competence Inventory (ESCI) is created to assess competencies that distinguish exceptional from average performers. The ESCI measures the behavior of individuals through their perceptions and the perceptions of those assessing them, distinguishing it from EI measures that assess ability or personality traits. Scores show participants how others perceive their behavior in terms of the consistency with which they demonstrate emotional and social competencies. The competencies are reduced to 12, grouped into 4 factors. Changes in the dimensions on which they are scored and their grouping are discussed in *Table 1*.

Table 1 Comparison between EC11.0, ECI 2.0 and ESCI

Cluster	ECI 1.0 Competency	ECI 2.0 Competency	ESCI Competency
Self Awareness	Emotional Self-Awareness	Emotional Self-Awareness	Emotional Self-Awareness
	Accurate Self-Assessment	Accurate Self-Assessment	
	Self-Confidence	Self-Confidence	
Self Management	Self-Control	Emotional Self-Control	Emotional Self-Control
		Transparency	
	Trustworthiness		
	Conscientiousness		
	Adaptability	Adaptability	Adaptability
		Optimism	Positive Outlook
	Achievement Orientation	Achievement	Achievement Orientation
Social Awareness	Initiative	Initiative	
	Empathy	Empathy	Empathy
	Organizational Awareness	Organizational Awareness	
Relationship Management	Service Orientation	Service Orientation	Organizational Awareness
	Developing Others	Developing Others	Coach And Mentor
	Leadership	Inspirational Leadership	Inspirational Leadership
	Influence	Influence	Influence
	Communication		
	Change Catalyst	Change Catalyst	
	Conflict Management	Conflict Management	Conflict Management
	Building Bonds		
Teamwork And Collaboration	Teamwork & Collaboration	Teamwork	

Source: Own

EQ-I Model by Ruven Bar-On

The theoretical Bar-On model is the basis for the creation of the Emotional Quotient Inventory (EQ-I), which is also the main research tool to this model. The EQ-I is a self-report based methodology that determines the level of emotional and social intelligence. The EQ-I was the first psychological test of its kind at the time of its publication (Bar-On, 1997) that indicates the level of subjective emotional and social intelligence and reveals features of socially competent behavior of an individual. There are five components that the author includes in his theoretical model (*these scales are illustrated in Table 2*):

1. Intrapersonal skills (including self-esteem, emotional self-awareness, self-actualization, independence and self-worth);
2. Interpersonal skills (including empathy, social responsibility and interpersonal relationships);
3. Stress management skills (including tolerance of stressful situations and controlling one's own impulsivity);
4. Adaptability skills (including flexibility and problem-solving abilities);
5. General mood (including qualities that maintain optimism and happiness).

Description of EQ-I

This method contains 133 items in the form of short statements, with respondents using a five-point Likert scale with limits ranging from "this does not apply to me" to "this is completely true for me." According to the author, the test takes about 40 minutes to complete and is suitable for individuals 17 years of age and older. Five components were identified in the theoretical model, and for research purposes they were decomposed into 15 scales distributed as follows in the table.

Measuring Trait EI

In 2000, Adrian Furnham and Konstantin Petrides presented an in-depth analysis of the various existing models of emotional intelligence, following the conceptual framework that emotional intelligence is a personality trait and attempting to prove the validity of this thesis. They conceptually confirm the distinction between models of emotional intelligence as a capability, mixed models of emotional intelligence, and the assumptions about emotional intelligence as a personality trait that have been slow to enter scientific circles.

Table 2 I scales and what they assess

EQ-I Scales	The EI Competencies and Skills Assessed by Each Scale
Intra personal	Self-awareness and self-expression:
Self-Regard	<i>To accurately perceive, understand and accept oneself.</i>
Emotional Self-Awareness	<i>To be aware of and understand one's emotions.</i>
Assertiveness	<i>To effectively and constructively express one's emotions and oneself.</i>
Independence	<i>To be self-reliant and free of emotional dependency on others</i>
Self- Actualization	<i>To strive to achieve personal goals and actualize one's potential</i>
Interpersonal	Social awareness and interpersonal relationship:
Empathy	<i>To be aware of and understand how others feel.</i>
Social Responsibility	<i>To identify with one's social group and cooperate with others.</i>
Interpersonal Relationship	<i>To establish mutually satisfying relationships and relate well with others.</i>
Stress Management	Emotional management and regulation:
Stress Tolerance	<i>To effectively and constructively manage emotions.</i>
Impulse Control	<i>To effectively and constructively control emotions.</i>
Adaptability	Change management:
Reality-Testing	<i>To objectively validate one's feelings and thinking with external reality.</i>
Flexibility	<i>To adapt and adjust one's feelings and thinking to new situations.</i>
Problem-Solving	<i>To effectively solve problems of a personal and interpersonal nature.</i>
General Mood	Self-motivation:
Optimism	<i>To be positive and look at the brighter side of life.</i>
Happiness	<i>To feel content with oneself others and life in general.</i>

Source: (Monselise et al, 2013)

EI measurement with TEIQue

Originally, the authors Petrides and Furnham revised Schutte's emotional intelligence measurement scale (Schutte et al., 1998) and added it to the Bar-On method (EQ-I). Subsequent (Monselise et al., 2013) unsatisfactory research results with the Bar-On method have raised questions about the psychometric properties and validity of the method. With the idea of developing it further to improve its psychometric qualities, the authors added a new scale to the core scales, which they called

"emotional power," as well as several items relating to the ability to identify and regulate the emotions of others. In a number of verifications of a modified version of the Bar-On method, Petrides and Furnham report some weaknesses in psychometric measurement. Analysing the strengths of some of the components, eliminating others, adding new items, and creating the first version of a questionnaire about emotional intelligence as a personality trait, the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire TEIQue (v. 1.00), which consists of 144 questions (Petrides and Furnham, 2001). TEIQue is conditioned by the theory and model of EI, the concept of which is based on individual traits localized at the lowest level of the hierarchy of individual traits. The subsequent validation of the instrument, which lasted several years, aimed to verify the validity of the method and to compare it with other personality methods. Subsequently, after repeated measurements and additions of new items, they refined the first version of the method and thus created the TEIQue method (v. 1.50), which is the full version of a comprehensive multidimensional personality test. The method contains 153 items constructed in 15 subscales, which are grouped in 4 scales - "Well-being", "Self-control", "Sociability" and "Emotionality". As described by the authors, the method's items aim to measure an individual's assessment of the effectiveness of the beliefs by which he or she perceives, processes, and uses information related to emotions in everyday life. The TEIQue method (v. 1.50) is constructed as a self-report personality questionnaire.

ALTERNATIVE METHODS FOR MEASURING EI

Objectivity and reflecting on the subject in full, it is necessary to specify that there are not a few instruments for measuring emotional intelligence. Currently, more than 30 different widely used measures of EI have been developed (O'Connor et al., 2019) and new ones continue to be proposed. There are also those whose authors are based on findings derived and described by established researchers in the field, and as a consequence do not contribute to theoretical understandings, but rather use existing models to develop their own measure. It would be difficult to cover in detail all possible measures, so some of the more popular ones will be mentioned. As alternative instruments for measuring EI the following can be mentioned:

- **Trait Meta-Mood Scale (TMMS)** – one of the first measures of EI, based on the original Salovey and Mayer model (Salovey, Mayer and Goldman, 1995). EI research using the TMMS can be thought of as measuring the attention we pay to our emotions, the clarity with which we distinguish between different emotions, and our confidence that we can control them (restore our good mood) (Salovey et al., 1995). The TMMS assesses an individual's relatively stable attitudes toward and control over their feelings.
- **The Schutte Emotional Intelligence Scale (SEIS) or Self Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SREIT)** – has between 3 and 4 factors, with the main drawback being that it provides incomplete coverage of EI, relying heavily on the three dimensions postulated in the original 1990 Salovey and Mayer model (Schutte, Malouff and Bobik, 2001). However, it is used extensively in the literature as it is one of the few free instruments but can be defined as a parsimonious measure of overall EI.
- **Workgroup Emotional Intelligence Profile (WEIP-3)** – a measure designed to examine the EI of individuals in workgroups. Early research shows that teams possessing high levels of EI tend to perform better than teams with low (Jordan, Ashkanasy and Hartel, 2002).
- **Emotional Intelligence Self-Regulation Scale (EISRS)** – based on the Martinez-Pons (2000) model of EI self-regulation, which integrates Bandura's theory of social cognition and the original Salovey and Mayer model.
- **The Dulewicz & Higgs Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (DHEIQ)** – is based on books by Goleman and is designed for use in organizational settings (Dulewicz and Higgs, 2001).
- **Sjoberg Personality Test Battery (SPTB)** – an extensive instrument measuring many different individual constructs and aspects, including emotional intelligence. The comprehensive toolkit (full version) includes 789 items corresponding to the 7- point Likert scale, grouped into 21 scales (Sjöberg, 2001).

- **Work Place Swinburne University Emotional Intelligence Test** (*Work-place SUEIT*) – is a concept measure designed for use in the workplace. It derives a total score by scoring five empirically defined subscales: 'emotional recognition and display', 'understanding emotions', 'direct knowledge of emotions', 'managing emotions' and 'emotional control' (Palmer, and Stough, 2002).
 - **Wong & Law Emotional Intelligence Scale** (WLEIS) – designed to quickly measure EI for use in organizational research. The WLEIS is a self-report measure that consists of 16 items to measure EI based on Mayer and Salovey's revised model. The authors report good internal consistency and reliability of their measure (Wong and Law,2002). In terms of validity, they present data showing that WLEIS scores are related to job performance and job satisfaction.
 - **The Genos Emotional Intelligence Inventory** - Genos EI was created in 2008 by researchers at Australia's Swinburne University. They maintain that no model exists that is applicable to workplace practice and serves as a tool to be used by human resource professionals (Gignac, 2008). It is with this in mind that they created their model, as specifically designed for use by HR professionals, aimed specifically at the work environment and issues related to it. The Genos EI inventory, is not designed to measure EI according to traditional understandings, but takes an entirely different approach to the concept of measuring it. The model focuses on the frequency with which an individual display emotionally intelligent behavior and the extent to which it is characteristic of that individual. The reason for the changed focus of the model, the creators defend, is that organizations are more interested in how much emotionally intelligent behavior is characteristic of a particular individual in the organization than in achieving a single, albeit high, score. The six emotionally intelligent competencies of the Genos model are Self-Awareness, Awareness of Others, Authenticity, Emotional Reasoning, Self-Management, and Positive Influence (Gignac, 2019).
 - Geneva Emotional Competence Test (GEC_o) by Schlegel and Mortillaro (2018) is an online-only performance-based test to measure individual differences in emotional intelligence in the context of the workplace and organizations. GEC_o defines 4 central competencies: Emotion Recognition; Emotion Understanding; Emotion Management and Emotion Regulation. The GEC_o test is designed specifically for the workplace and organizations and the 110 items include 42 short video clips.
 - The Six Seconds Emotional Intelligence Assessment (SEI) is unique in that it focuses on the application of emotional intelligence, offering a framework for a process of putting emotional intelligence into action (Freedman et al., 2005). The toolkit was developed by an international team and is available in 26 different languages. The model consists of eight core competencies divided into three key aspirations - Know Yourself (self-awareness); Choose Yourself (self-management) and Give Yourself (self-direction).
 - The Profile of Emotional Competence (PEC) was developed by Brasseur and Mikolajczak (2013) to measure intrapersonal EI and interpersonal EI separately. It assesses the five core emotional competencies (identification, understanding, expression, regulation and use of emotions) separately for one's own emotions and for the emotions of others. There is also a short form in which the 50 questions are reduced to 20, but only total EI is reported.
- Some of the mentioned tools fail to establish themselves over time remain presented and researched mainly by their authors. Genos EI faces serious criticism due to the discrepancy between the understanding of the generally recognized names in this field and the innovative idea of the authors. Criticism can also be levelled at some of the other models. The TMMS does not fully cover the concept of emotional intelligence, the DHEIQ has not been used much in the scientific literature and there is very little information about its reliability and validity, and the EISRS is not known to be a validated scale in the scientific literature (e.g. Pérez et al., 2005). Further information on the instruments regarding their reliability, structure, items, etc. is provided in the comparative Table 3.

Table 3 Overview of the EI measures

Measure	Authors (year)	Cronbach alpha	Factors, domains / facets, competencies	Structure	Statements / questions included	Likert scale
TMMS	Salovey Mayer Goldman Turvey Palfai (1995)	0,70-0,85	3	Attention to Feelings, Clarity in Discrimination of Feelings, Mood Repair	48 / 30 / 24*	5-point
EQ-I 1.0 / EQ-I 2.0	Bar-On (1997 / 2000)	Generally good (about 0,85)	5/15	Intrapersonal Interpersonal Stress management Adaptability General mood	133 / 125	5-point
SEIS / SSEIT	Schutte (1998)	0,70-0,85	3	Appraisal and expression of emotion Regulation of emotion Utilization of emotion	33	5-point
ECI 1.0 ECI 2.0	Boyatzis, Goleman (1999 / 2002)	0.70–0.85 / 0,68-0,87	4/20 4/18	Self-awareness Social awareness Self-management Relationship management	110 / 72	7-point / 6-point
EISRS	Martinez-Pons (2000)	0,75-0,94	4/11	Motivation Goal Setting Strategy Self- Evaluation	52	7-point
DHEIQ	Dulewicz&Higgs (2001)	Low to moderate (0.54-0,71)	7/	Self-awareness Emotional Resilience Motivation Interpersonal Sensitivity Influence Intuitiveness Conscientious	69	-
MSCEIT	Mayer-Salovey-Caruso (1997 / 2002)	Better for Version 2 than Version 1 (0.68–0.71)	4/8	Perceiving emotions Facilitating thought Understanding emotions Managing emotions	141	5-point
TEIQue	Petrides & Furnham (2001)	Generally good (about 0.85)	4/15	Well-being Self-control Emotionality Sociability	153	7-point
SPTB	Sjöberg (2001)	0,70-0,85	4 / 21		789	4-poin

MSCEIT	Mayer-Salovey-Caruso (1997 / 2002)	Better for Version 2 than Version 1 (0.68–0.71)	4/8	Perceiving emotions Facilitating thought Understanding emotions Managing emotions	141	5-point
TEIQue	Petrides & Furnham (2001)	about 0.85	4/15	Well-being Self-control Emotionality Sociability	153	7-point
SUEIT	Palmer, Stough (2002)	Generally good (about 0.85)	5/	Emotional Recognition and Expression Understanding Emotions External Emotions Direct Cognition Emotional Management Emotional Control	64	5-point
WEIP-3	Jordan Ashkanasy Härtelb Hooper (2002)	0,70-0,85	2 / 7	Ability to Deal with Own Emotions Ability to Deal with Others' Emotions	30	7-point
WLEIS	Wong, Law (2003)	0,70-0,85	4 /	Self-emotion appraisal Others' emotion appraisal Use of emotion Regulation of emotion	16	5-point
TEIQue - SF	Petrides & Furnham (2004)	0.83- 0.93	4 /15	Well-being Self-control Emotionality Sociability	30	7-point
SEI	Ghini, Freedman, Jensen 2004		3/8	Self-awareness Self-management Self-direction	104	5-point
ESCI v1 ESCI v2	Boyatzis, Goleman (2007 / 2011)	0,73 – 0,92	4/12	Self-awareness Social awareness Self-management Relationship management	68	5-point
PEC	Brasseur and Mikolajczak (2013)	0,72 – 0,92	2 / 5	Intra-personal EI Inter-personal EI	50	5-point
GEC0	Schlegel & Mortillaro (2018)		4	Emotion recognition Emotion understanding Emotion management Emotion regulation	110	correct or wrong response

*depending on the instrument version

Source: based on information from <http://www.eiconsortium.org/measures/measures.html>; <https://psychometriclab.com/publications/> and the sources cited in the text

As a serious drawback, it is sometimes interpreted that EI as a personality trait is related to the foundations of primary personality dimensions and does not always contribute to the gradual prediction of criterion variance (MacCan et al., 2004). This critique should be put in perspective by

emphasizing once again that conceptualizing EI as a lower personality trait will eventually influence it to be related to higher personality dimensions (Petrides and Furnham, 2001). Indeed, it would be quite strange if a lower personality construct, were unrelated to higher personality dimensions that determine the factor of the space it occupies. It is true, as researchers have repeatedly noted, that no type of EI reflects the expectations constructed in the literature (Cooper, 1997). However, it is also true that discriminant and partial structure validity are beyond any empirical doubt (Saklofske et al., 2003).

A related issue is the modelling domain on which the various measures of EI (as a capability and as a personality trait) are based. The first step in operationalizing the psychological structure involves defining the items that comprise this domain. Virtually all EI models, questionnaires, and tests have skipped this step, suggesting arbitrarily chosen domains. In the vast majority of cases, the inclusion or exclusion of aspects is the result of unproven or arbitrary processes. Also noteworthy is the fact that many of the facets may sound different but are functionally the same. On the elements they cover, the different EI models are complementary rather than contradictory (Ciarrochi, 2000).

CHOOSING A MEASUREMENT FOR EI

The elements that comprise the different models of emotional intelligence are complementary rather than contradictory. Also noteworthy is the fact that many of the aspects may sound different but are functionally the same. Furthermore, the major models of EI share quite a few major aspects, although they also include aspects that are not central to the structure.

Goleman never substantiated his theoretical grounds for the membership of the abilities in the structure of emotional intelligence in his original models. He confined himself to interpreting competence merely as the individual's ability to operate with his emotions in a situationally appropriate way in order to integrate into the social environment. For this reason, he defines this kind of abilities as social competencies and includes them in the structure of emotional intelligence. There are obvious flaws in his position, and one of them is that, according to him, emotional intelligence is present when a person demonstrates certain competencies. Competence, on the other hand, can be viewed by not addressing emotional-affective but rather cognitive-content components. In this direction, it is adequate to understand why early proponents of the idea that emotional intelligence is a type of social competence associated it primarily with cognitive mastery of the external environment and enhancement of adaptive capacities of mental regulation. However, the model has great popularity and a measurement methodology based on this model can be included as one of the main alternatives in selecting an approach.

CONCLUSION

It is clear from the comparative analysis that the debate in the scientific literature continues to be between models viewing EI as an ability and as a personality trait. The choice of approach should be limited to a few basic instruments. It is logical in this situation that the described derivations of the basic models should be considered situationally if desired by those applying the methodology. If they are interested in a broader set of emotion-related and social-related dispositions and competencies probably a mixed measure would be the most appropriate. If the researchers/practitioners are interested in measuring behavioral tendencies and/or emotional self-efficacy a trait measures of EI be should selected (O'Connor, 2019). When both abilities and traits are important, then both ability and trait measures might be chosen.

Other criteria can be identified that would influence the choice of an approach to study emotional intelligence. The main such criteria would be the accessibility of the methodology; whether overall EI is important or the results on individual items are relevant; whether it is adapted to the language; the time required to conduct the survey; the reliability of the results obtained; the subjective understandings of theoretical models of EI by the person making the choice; the limitations of third party choice, etc.

For some of the tools, it is worth noting that they do not yet have cross-language adaptation, and consequently there are certain limitations in their willingness to be used. In order to make a qualitative adaptation, experts with in-depth knowledge of the respective foreign language and of course in psychology are needed in order to be able to form the questions as correctly as possible.

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